

Production Performance of Broiler Farms with Partnership Model in Malang District

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ABSTRACT: Broiler farming has an essential role in meeting national protein needs and improving the economic resilience of rural communities. The partnership pattern between farmers and core companies is the dominant system in broiler business management in East Java Province, especially Malang District. The study aimed to evaluate the production performance and financial efficiency of broiler farms in the partnership system. The research was conducted using a case study approach and quantitative methods with 75 farmers from Dunia Makmur Sejahtera's plasma partners, spread across twelve districts. Respondents varied in age, education, farming experience, and scale of chicken population categorized into three business strata. Production performance indicators analyzed included feed conversion ratio (FCR), average body weight (ABW), mortality rate, harvest age, and performance index (IP). The financial evaluation included total cost, revenue, profit per cycle, and revenue to cost ratio (R/C ratio). Results showed that the average FCR was 1.79, ABW was 2.13 kg, depletion rate was 4.5%, and IP value reached 325. Based on stratification analysis, large-scale farms (Stratum III) showed better technical performance and financial efficiency than small and medium-scale strata. Financial efficiency was generally low with an average R/C ratio of 0.87. This suggests that despite promising technical performance, farmers still face serious challenges in achieving sustainable profitability. These findings emphasize the importance of improved feeding management, enhanced biosecurity and a re-evaluation of partnership contract schemes that are more equitable, especially for small and medium-scale farmers, to improve broiler performance and profitability in the future.

KEYWORDS: Broiler farming, performance index, feed conversion ratio, farm scale, financial efficiency, partnership model.

INTRODUCTION

The livestock sector is one of the important sub-sectors in Indonesia's agricultural development that plays a role in providing animal protein for the community and supporting national economic growth. One of the main commodities that has a major contribution in fulfilling animal protein needs is broilers, due to its fast growth, high feed conversion efficiency, and relatively short harvest period. Demand for chicken meat continues to increase in line with population growth, urbanisation, and rising incomes.

Malang Regency is one of the broiler production centres in East Java Province. The broiler farming business system in this area is mostly carried out through a partnership pattern in which plasma farmers cooperate with core companies in terms of providing production facilities (sapronek), technical guidance, and marketing of crops. This partnership pattern is expected to increase the productivity and efficiency of the farming business, especially for small and medium-scale farmers.

The effectiveness of partnerships and the success of broiler farms are strongly influenced by technical production performance, such as feed conversion ratio (FCR), chicken body weight at harvest, mortality rate, harvest age, and performance index (IP). Variations in housing management, feed quality, animal health and adherence to standard operating procedures greatly affect production yields and farmer profits.

In addition to technical aspects, variables such as total production costs, revenue, net profit, and revenue-to-cost ratio (R/C ratio) are important indicators in assessing the success of a broiler farming business. Good financial performance not only ensures business continuity in the short term but also increases the competitiveness and capacity of farmers in the long term. The assessment of business efficiency cannot be separated from a combination of technical and economic analyses. Farmers' socioeconomic characteristics such as age, education level, farming experience and business scale influence technical and financial decision-making in broiler rearing practices. Understanding these characteristics is important to formulate appropriate and sustainable coaching strategies in a partnership system.

The study aimed to evaluate the production performance and financial efficiency of Dunia Makmur Sejahtera broiler farms in Malang District. The main focus was on technical indicators such as FCR, harvest weight, mortality, harvest age, and performance index, as well as economic indicators such as production cost, revenue, profit and R/C ratio. The results of the study are expected to provide a real picture of the effectiveness of partnership patterns and provide applicable managerial recommendations in increasing the productivity and efficiency of smallholder farming in a sustainable manner.

METHOD

The study used a survey method with a quantitative approach, which aims to analyse the production performance and financial efficiency of broiler farms in partnership patterns. Primary data were collected through the distribution of structured questionnaires to plasma farmers who are members of the partnership with Dunia Makmur Sejahtera in Malang Regency.

The criteria for respondents in the study were farmers who had run a broiler business partnership for at least one year and were active in maintenance activities during one full production cycle. The number of respondents in the study was 75 farmers, spread across several sub-districts of broiler production centres in Malang District.

Data were collected directly through visits to the barn, guided interviews, and production documentation. Data were collected after the Eid al-Fitr holiday in April. The questionnaire used contained questions about farmer profiles (age, education, farming experience, number of family members), technical production data (population, harvest weight, feed consumption, harvest age, mortality, and IP), and business economic data (fixed costs, variable costs, revenue, profit, and R/C ratio).

The sampling technique used was purposive sampling, which is a technique for selecting respondents based on certain criteria that are considered relevant and representative for research purposes (Sugiyono, 2019).

The data obtained were analysed descriptively quantitatively, by presenting averages and percentages. Production performance and business efficiency were also analysed based on the grouping of business scale into three strata (Strata I, II, III) to see differences in results based on cage population capacity.

DATA ANALYSIS

To understand the conceptual context and the best approach in achieving the research objectives, the following analyses to evaluate the economic viability of the farm business are included:

- Production Performance Analysis

- a. ABW

Average body weight (ABW) at harvest is an important indicator that describes the growth outcome of broilers during the rearing cycle (Khan et al., 2020). Weight reflects the effectiveness of feeding, health management and genetics of the birds being reared (Güçlü et al., 2019). The ideal harvest weight usually ranges from 2.0 to 2.5 kg per bird within 35-42 days. An optimal ABW indicates that production is efficient and the profit potential of the farm can be maximised.

$$ABW = \frac{\text{Total Bobot Panen (kg)}}{\text{Populasi Panen (ekor)}}$$

- b. FCR

Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) is the ratio between the amount of feed consumed and the body weight produced by broiler chickens. FCR is a parameter of feed efficiency, where lower values indicate more efficient use of feed in producing chicken weight (Santos et al., 2021). The ideal FCR for broilers ranges from 1.5 to 1.8 depending on the strain and rearing conditions. Good feed management and good animal health can lower FCR values, thereby reducing production costs and increasing profitability (Alabi et al., 2019).

$$FCR = \frac{\text{Total pakan yang diberikan (kg)} - \text{total sisa pakan (kg)}}{\text{Total bobot ayam yang dihasilkan (kg)}}$$

- c. Depleksi

Depletion or mortality and culling rates is the percentage of chickens that die or have to be culled during the rearing period. Depletion or mortality rate describes the percentage of chicken deaths during rearing which is an important indicator in health assessment and cage management (Rahman et al., 2023). Kebede et al. (2020) revealed that low

mortality (<5%) signifies effective disease control and a conducive cage environment. Conversely, high mortality increases production costs and decreases efficiency.

$$\text{Depletion} = \frac{(\text{Jumlah ayam mati} + \text{culling})}{\text{Populasi awal}} \times 100\%$$

d. Harvest Age

Harvest age is the time or day when broilers are harvested after the rearing period. The optimal harvest age usually ranges from 35 to 42 days, depending on production goals and market conditions (Iqbal et al., 2022). Harvesting at the right time allows chickens to reach optimal weight with good feed efficiency. Harvesting too early can reduce weight and revenue, while harvesting too late increases rearing costs and health risks.

$$\text{Umur} = \frac{\text{Jumlah ayam panen (ekor)} \times \text{Umur panen (hari)}}{\text{Total ayam panen (ekor)}}$$

e. Performance Index

The Performance Index (IP) is a composite measure that combines several performance indicators such as growth, FCR, mortality, and harvest age to provide an overall picture of broiler production efficiency (Mustafa et al., 2020). A high IP indicates good quality of rearing management and a productive farming enterprise. The index helps farmers and business managers to evaluate and make strategic decisions to improve productivity and business efficiency.

$$\text{IP} = \frac{(100 - \text{Depletion})\% \times \text{BB rata-rata}}{\text{FCR} \times \text{Umur panen (hari)}} \times 100$$

• Profit and Loss Analysis

a. Production Cost

Total Cost

Total cost is the overall expenditure to run a business to produce output (Sari, et al., 2023). The costs incurred for farming are divided into two, namely variable costs and fixed costs. Fixed costs do not depend on the volume of production, or it can be said that the amount of costs is not affected by changes in the number of goats produced, while variable costs are costs that change according to the number of livestock (Anwar, et al., 2023). Total fixed costs in the study consist of fixed costs which are the cost of cage depreciation and non-fixed costs which are the cost of livestock maintenance needs during the business..

$$TC = FC + VC$$

Description:

TC : Total cost (IDR/period)

FC : Fixed cost (IDR/period)

VC : Variable cost (IDR/period)

b. Revenue

Revenue is the money received by a company from the business it runs. Mathematical revenue is the multiplication of products sold by the price per unit of the product. Labatar, et al. (2023) revenue is written as follows:

$$TR = P \times Q$$

Description:

TR : Total revenue (IDR/period)

P : Product price (IDR/period)

Q : Quantity

c. Profit

Revenue or profit is the difference between revenue and total expenses in a business (Evadewi et al. 2021).

$$\pi = TR - TC$$

Description:

- π : Profit (IDR/period)
- TR : Total Revenue (IDR/period)
- TC : Total Cost (IDR/period)

• Profitability analysis

Financial analysis is the activity of analysing the finances of a business by comparing expenses (costs) with profits (benefits), so that the return value of a business can be known. The financial feasibility analysis used in the study used the R/C Ratio indicator.

a. R/C Ratio (Return Cost Ratio)

R/C Ratio is the ratio between income and expenditure costs (Soekartawi, 2005). The use of R/C Ratio can determine whether a business is profitable or not (Moni, et al., 2024).

$$R/C \text{ Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Revenue}}{\text{Total Cost}}$$

R/C can draw conclusions including:

- If R/C Ratio > 1, then the business is profitable.
- If R/C Ratio = 1, then the revenue is equal to BEP.
- If the R/C Ratio < 1, then the business is at a loss.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Broiler Farmer Characteristics Based on Age

Respondents in the study were grouped into three age categories, namely: unproductive age (≤ 15 years), productive age (16-64 years), and unproductive age (> 64 years) (Hartono, 2006). The distribution results showed that most farmers were in the productive age category, as many as 61 people (or 81.3%). This group consists of farmers aged between 26 to 55 years old who are physically active and generally have the ability to adapt to technical innovations, such as feed management and biosecurity.

Table 1. Percentage of Farmer Age

No	Age	Number of Farmers (People)	%
1	≤ 15	0	0
2	16-64	62	82,7
3	> 64	13	17,3
Amount		75	100

In general, the dominance of productive age indicates that broiler farming in Malang District still has a large pool of physical and managerial potential. This region has a strong potential for growth, so productive-age farmers in this region are the main key in driving the growth and competitiveness of the broiler farming sector in a sustainable manner. They need to be supported with technical training and coaching to strengthen their capacity to face the challenges of an increasingly competitive business. Brata et al. (2020) stated that livestock business development can be supported by the productive age of farmers.

Broiler Farmer Characteristics Based on Education

Based on the education data of the plasma farmer respondents obtained in the study, the characteristics of the farmer's education level show quite diverse variations. The majority of farmers have the latest education at the senior high school level, as many as 30 people (40%).

Table 2. Percentage of Farmer Education

No	Education level	Number of Farmers (People)	%
1	Elementary School	12	16
2	Junior High School	25	33,3
3	Senior High School	30	40
4	Bachelor	8	10,7
Amount		75	100

The data shows that most farmers have an appropriate formal education background, especially at the secondary level, so they have the potential to understand and implement technology and business management in broiler partnerships effectively. The presence of farmers with low education levels remains a concern as it may affect their ability to make decisions and adapt to technical innovations. There is a need for more intensive training and mentoring for groups of farmers with low education so that they can improve their managerial and technical skills, thus supporting the overall success of the livestock business. Rohmah (2021) revealed that farmers with higher formal education (such as high school and university) are more capable of managing their businesses efficiently and are more open to training and adoption of the latest technology in their businesses.

Broiler Farmer Characteristics Based on Experience

Based on data on breeding experience from 75 plasma farmer respondents involved in the study, most farmers have a variety of breeding experience. The group with 10-20 years of experience is the largest, namely 28 people (37.3%).

Table 3. Percentage of Farming Experience

No	Length of Farming (Years)	Number of Farmers (People)	%
1	< 5	10	13,4
2	5 – 10	22	29,3
3	10 – 20	28	37,3
4	20 – 30	15	20
Amount		75	100

Farming experience plays an important role in technical and managerial decision-making and improves farmers' capacity to maintain production resilience and new technological innovations. Farmers with more than 10 years of experience allow for a more mature understanding of feed management, disease control, and pen management, thereby improving business efficiency and productivity. The diversity of experience levels indicates the need for a customised training approach, where novice farmers receive more intensive support to increase their capacity, while experienced farmers receive the latest knowledge and technology updates to continuously improve the quality and efficiency of their broiler enterprises. Akinmoladun et al. (2014) showed that farmers with more than 10 years of experience tended to better understand farm management techniques and disease control, which in turn increased production yields.

Broiler Farmer Characteristics Based on Business Scale

Farmers are classified into three business strata based on the size of the livestock population, namely: Strata I with a population between 2,000 and 17,333 head, Strata II with a population of 17,334 to 32,666 head, and Strata III with a population of 32,667 to 48,000 head. The data shows that the majority of farmers are in Strata I, which is a group with a small to medium scale business, totalling 30 farmers (40%).

Table 4. Percentage of Farmer Business Scale

No	Scale	Number of Farmers (People)	%
1	Strata I	30	40
2	Strata II	28	37
3	Strata III	17	23
Amount		75	100

Strata I farmer groups have limited capital and management capacity and therefore tend to face challenges in production efficiency and technology application. Nugroho and Hadi (2018) mentioned that small-scale farmers have the potential to increase productivity if given assistance in terms of access to capital and training in production management. This characteristic is also reflected in stratum I farmers, who make up a relatively large proportion (40%) of the population. Meanwhile, stratum II farmers who manage a medium population with a larger capacity allow them to implement better production management and obtain more favourable economies of scale. The stratum III group has more adequate capital and resources to optimise the use of technology, feed management and more intensive livestock health monitoring. This contributes to better production performance compared to the other two strata.

Production Performance of Broiler Farms

Performance indicators of broiler farms in the partnership model in East Java, particularly in Malang District, show moderate to good technical efficiency. These variables include Average Body Weight (ABW) as an indicator of the average growth of chickens, Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) which measures the efficiency of feed use, depletion rate (mortality rate) which reflects the health and management of cages, harvest age which determines the optimal time for harvesting, and Performance Index (IP) as a measure that describes farm performance.

a. Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR)

The overall average FCR achieved was 1.79 indicating that broilers require 1.79 kg of feed to produce 1 kg of live weight although it is still within acceptable industry standards. The table shows the highest average FCR (Feed Conversion Ratio) value in the three strata of broiler farms with a partnership model in Malang District, which reached 1.95 in stratum I, the lowest FCR was in stratum III farmers who reached 1.62. This indicates that there is room for improvement in stratum I broiler farms.

Table 5. Rataan FCR

No	Keterangan	Strata I	Strata II	Strata III
1	Rataan Pakan Dikonsumsi (kg)	27.000	46.000	66.000
2	Rataan Bobot Panen (kg)	16.200	27.200	43.200
Rataan FCR		1,95	1,78	1,62

Efficient FCR values are generally between 1.5 and 1.7 indicating that feed management practices on the observed farms could benefit from optimisation in terms of timing, ration composition and frequency of feeding. Based on Table 5, it can be observed that the mean FCR value decreased from stratum I to stratum III. The decrease in FCR value indicates an increase in feed use efficiency in stratum III broiler farms. This can be interpreted that in stratum III farms on average require 1.62 kg of feed to produce 1 kg of live weight. The higher mean FCR value in stratum I indicates lower feed use efficiency than stratum II and III. This can occur because the maintenance management in stratum I is less than optimal. This can be caused by several factors such as improper feeding techniques, lower feed quality, or improper maintenance management (Garcia et al., 2019).

b. Average Body Weight (ABW) at Harvest

The overall average ABW recorded was 2.13kg per bird which is quite satisfactory for the standard harvest age (35-36 days). Based on the table, it can be seen that the average harvest weight (ABW) of broilers showed a significant increase with rearing strata. These results reflect the potential of the partnership model to support optimal growth when combined with good feeding and environmental control.

Table 6. ABW rate

No	Keterangan	Strata I	Strata II	Strata III
1	Rataan Bobot Panen (kg)	16.120	28.300	44.500
2	Rataan Populasi Panen (ekor)	7.900	13.000	20.500
	Rataan ABW (kg)	2.04	2.18	2.17

The average body weight (ABW) of broilers across strata shows that Strata II and Strata III have nearly identical ABW values of approximately 2.18 kg and 2.17 kg, respectively, while Strata I has a lower ABW of 2.04 kg. This indicates that, on an individual basis, the body weight of chickens in Strata II and III tends to be more optimal and uniform compared to Strata I. The difference in average body weight between the strata is not significant, meaning that the large disparity in total harvest weight between the strata is more influenced by the population size of the chickens harvested. The increase in total broiler harvest weight is attributed to the number of chickens produced relative to the average body weight per bird. A study in Poland also confirms that while the body weight of individual chickens remains relatively stable, production efficiency and profitability remain high (Nowak et al., 2024).

c. Depleksi Rate

Based on the data table, there is a clear difference between the three strata. The highest depletion rate is found in the broiler farming business in Stratum I. In Stratum I, the average number of chickens that died and were culled reached 432 birds from an initial population of 8,320 birds, resulting in an average depletion rate of 5.2%.

Table 7. Rataan Depleksi

No	Keterangan	Strata I	Strata II	Strata III
1	Rataan Jumlah Ayam Mati + Culling (ekor)	432	650	825
2	Rataan Populasi Awal (ekor)	8.320	14.444	21.148
	Rataan Depleksi (%)	5,2	4,5	3,9

The data on the average depletion rate of broiler chickens in Malang Regency shows a downward trend in depletion percentages as the farming strata increase. This decline indicates that farmers with larger chicken populations and more structured management tend to have better maintenance efficiency, thus able to reduce mortality and culling rates. This is in line with the findings of Rahman et al. (2022), who stated that increasing the scale of operations and implementing optimal management can reduce depletion rates in broiler chickens. Furthermore, Wahyuni and Setiawan (2023) emphasized that factors such as cage management, feed provision, and disease control play a significant role in reducing mortality rates in large-scale farming. The difference in depletion rates between strata reflects the impact of scale and management quality in broiler chicken production, which affects the success of the farming operation. This indicates that biosecurity, disease control, and environmental conditions in most farms are managed quite well, although some units may still experience losses due to stress from inconsistent temperature control or delayed vaccinations. The overall mortality and culling rate across all strata averages 4.53%, slightly below the 5% threshold considered acceptable in commercial broiler farming. Kebede et al. (2020) revealed that low mortality (<5%) indicates effective disease control and a conducive farm environment. Conversely, high mortality increases production costs and reduces efficiency.

d. Harvest Age

The average harvest age of broiler farms overall in Malang Regency is 35.7 days. Based on Table 8 regarding the average harvest age of broilers in Malang Regency, it can be seen that there are differences in the average harvest age across the farming strata. Timely harvesting is crucial to avoid reduced feed efficiency and increased maintenance costs.

Stratum I with a longer harvest age of 36.1 days compared to the other strata, may face challenges in the optimal growth of the chickens, such as feed quality, cage management, or population density. In contrast, Stratum III is able to reach the ideal weight in a shorter time, which may indicate the implementation of better and more efficient management practices. This aligns with the research by Widodo et al. (2022), which stated that optimizing feed management, cage density, and environmental control can accelerate the harvest age of broilers without compromising their production performance. Additionally, according to the National Standardization

Agency (SNI 01-3920-2006), the harvest age of broiler chickens generally ranges from 30 to 36 days, depending on the strain type and quality of care. Therefore, all strata still fall within the normal range, although their efficiency differs.

Based on the average harvest age data for broiler chickens across the three strata in Malang Regency, it can be concluded that the core company plays an important role in determining production standards and efficiency, which serve as benchmarks for partner farmers in each stratum. The relatively uniform average harvest age, still within the normal range (around 35-36 days), indicates that the core company is able to provide technical guidance, maintenance management, and effective supervision for the contract farmers. This is reflected in the absence of significant or extreme differences in harvest age between strata, indicating the standardization of the production process applied by the core company.

e. Index Performance (IP)

The performance index of broiler farming across all strata in Malang Regency has an average of 325, exceeding the productivity threshold of 300. The performance index integrates weight growth, FCR, depletion, and harvest age. This indicates that broiler farming under the partnership model in Malang Regency operates at a commendable technical level.

Table 9. Rataan Indeks Performa

No	Keterangan	Strata I	Strata II	Strata III
1	Persentase ayam hidup	94,8	95,5	96,1
2	Rataan Bobot Panen (kg)	16.120	28.300	44.500
3	Rataan FCR	1,95	1,78	1,62
4	Rataan Umur Panen (hari)	36,1	35,7	35,4
Rataan Indeks Performa		305	325	345

Based on the Strata Performance Index, there is an improvement from Stratum I to Stratum III. Farms in higher strata (Stratum III) demonstrate better broiler performance in terms of survival rate, harvest weight, feed efficiency, and harvest age. The improvement as the strata increase is reflected in higher percentages of live chickens, larger harvest weights, more optimal feed efficiency (indicated by lower FCR values), and relatively stable and efficient harvest ages. This illustrates that the success in managing broiler farming is highly influenced by the level of investment, technology used, and better management in larger strata. Sihombing et al. (2020) showed that farms with larger capital and better facilities tend to have higher performance indices due to more structured and efficient management. Broiler farming under the partnership model in Malang Regency operates at a sufficient technical level and has the potential to yield optimal results, especially in strata with better capital and facilities.

Profitability of Broiler Farms

After analyzing the performance of broiler farming, it is important to examine how these factors contribute to the profitability of the business. These variables include production costs, revenue, profit, and the R/C (Revenue to Cost) ratio, which are key indicators in assessing the profitability of a farming operation.

a. Production Costs

Based on the data presented in Table 10, the total production costs of broiler farming in Malang Regency show differences across the strata. These differences indicate an increase in total production costs as well as a decrease in production costs per bird as the scale of the business increases in each stratum.

Table1 10. Rataan Biaya Produksi

Details	Strata I	Strata II	Strata III
Fixed Costs (penyusutan/bulan)			
Kandang (Rp)	25.483.870	105.555.600	163.764.700
Instalasi air (Rp)	9.556.452	39.583.330	61.411.760
Instalasi listrik (Rp)	5.415.323	22.430.560	34.800.000
Tempat pakan (Rp)	3.333	3.333	3.333
Tempat Minum (Rp)	28,70	28,70	28,70
Jumlah Biaya Tetap	40.459.010	167.572.800	259.979.800
Variable Costs			
DOC (Rp)	68.975.000	243.177.800	365.708.800
Pakan (Rp)	106.161.300	439.833.300	682.352.900
VOV (Rp)	2.647.750	9.334.889	14.038.500
Tenaga Kerja(Rp)	3.280.000	10.844.440	16.023.530
Jumlah Biaya Variabel (Rp/periode)	181.064.050	703.190.429	1,078,123,730
Total Biaya Produksi (Rp/periode)	221.523.060	870.763.229	1.338.103.530
Total Produksi (kg)	388.647,5	1.536.431,8	1.507.067,6
Biaya Produksi per kg (Rp/kg)	570	567	888

The comparison of production costs across strata shows significant variation in both fixed and variable costs. The increase in fixed costs with the expansion of the farming scale in Malang Regency is due to the rising variable costs associated with DOC, feed, VOV, and labor. Stratum III exhibits the highest production costs per period, which may be caused by the larger scale of operations and higher fixed costs. This is consistent with the findings of Wibowo and Hartono (2022), who stated that broiler production costs are heavily influenced by the scale of operations and the efficiency of input usage. Therefore, larger-scale farms do not necessarily achieve optimal cost efficiency due to the higher fixed and variable costs.

Based on the production costs per kg, broiler farming in Malang Regency shows that the production cost per kilogram of broiler varies across strata. The highest production cost per kg is found in Stratum III, at Rp. 888 per kg. This can affect profitability negatively due to the high production costs. The potential for operational inefficiencies, suboptimal use of technology, or high input costs may also contribute to increasing production costs. Febrianto and Putritamara (2018) revealed that efficient feed management and the optimal use of facilities can help reduce production costs.

b Revenue per Period

Based on the data presented in Table 11 regarding the revenue of broiler farming in Malang Regency, it can be seen that there are differences in revenue across the strata.

Table1 11. Average Revenue

No	Details	Unit	Strata I	Strata II	Strata III
1	Average Price of Live Chicken per kg	Rp	23.557	23.532	23.543
2	Average Production Quantity	kg	16.120	28.300	44.500
Average Revenue		Rp	379.738.840	665.955.600	1.047.663.500

Based on the average revenue data, it is evident that Stratum III has the highest average revenue of Rp 1,047,663,500. This significant difference is primarily caused by the substantial variation in average production quantity across strata. The larger

production volume in Stratum III is a key factor driving the significantly higher total revenue. The larger scale of operations in Stratum III also contributes to higher efficiency and production capacity, resulting in higher revenue compared to other strata. This aligns with the research by Putri et al. (2019), which stated that a larger business size not only increases production volume but also boosts total revenue due to better operational efficiency and the ability to accommodate more chickens in a single period.

b. Profit per kg

The average profit per production cycle across all strata in broiler farming in Malang Regency is negative, amounting to Rp. 112,343,960, indicating that some farmers are experiencing net losses. This is caused by production costs increasing at a faster rate than revenue.

Table1 12. Rataan Keuntungan per kg

No	Keterangan	Strata I	Strata II	Strata III
1	Average Revenue from Live Chicken (Rp)	379.738.840	665.955.600	1.047.663.500
2	Average Production Costs (Rp)	221.523.060	870.763.229	1.338.103.530
3	Production Profit per Period (Rp)	158.215.780	-204.807.629	-290.440.030
4	Total Production (kg)	388.647,5	1.536.431,8	1.507.067,6
Average Profit per kg (Rp/kg)		407,03	-133,27	-192,66

Based on the profit per kilogram, Strata II and Strata III are experiencing losses. This is because Strata II and Strata III have significantly higher average production costs compared to Strata I (Rp 870,763,229 and Rp 1,338,103,530 compared to Rp 221,523,060). This may be due to the larger scale of operations in Strata II and III, where increasing variable and fixed costs are not balanced by adequate revenue, leading to losses. Operations in Strata I are more efficient in managing production costs, feed usage, labor, and other management aspects, allowing them to keep costs lower than the larger strata. Putra et al. (2023) revealed that increasing business scale does not always guarantee higher profits if cost management is ineffective, especially in the broiler farming sector in Indonesia. The increase in business scale does not always align with increased profitability without adequate management efficiency. This phenomenon is consistent with findings in the broiler farming sector in Indonesia (Sari & Hidayat, 2022). Therefore, cost control strategies and improving operational efficiency are key to enhancing the profitability of medium and large-scale broiler businesses.

c. Revenue-Cost (R/C) Ratio

The overall average R/C ratio of broiler farming in Malang Regency is 0.86, indicating that, in general, broiler farming under this partnership model is not yet profitable, as revenue is still smaller than production costs. The R/C ratio is presented in Table 13.

Table1 13. R/C Ratio

No	Keterangan	Unit	Strata I	Strata II	Strata III
1	Average Revenue	Rp	379.738.840	665.955.600	1.047.663.500
2	Average Production Costs	Rp	221.523.060	870.763.229	1.338.103.530
R/C Ratio			1.71	0.76	0.78

Based on the average R/C ratio data for broiler farming under the partnership model in Malang Regency, it is evident that the average revenue and production costs differ significantly across the strata. The highest R/C ratio is recorded at 1.71 in Stratum I. This indicates that operations in Stratum I still generate a considerable profit and are efficient in terms of production cost utilization. Conversely, Strata II and III have R/C ratios of 0.76 and 0.78, respectively, indicating that operations in these strata are incurring losses, as the revenue generated is insufficient to cover production costs. This condition may result from various factors such as the larger scale of operations and higher production costs relative to revenue. Setiawan and Hidayat (2021) stated that broiler farming operations with smaller scales tend to have an R/C ratio above 1, indicating profitability, whereas large-scale operations tend to have an R/C ratio below 1 due to high production costs.

CONCLUSION

The analysis indicates that farms with better technical performance, such as more efficient feed usage (low FCR), higher chicken weight (high ABW), and a high performance index (PI), tend to yield better financial outcomes. However, these factors alone are not sufficient to guarantee profitability. The profitability of farms is heavily influenced by the volatility of input costs and the profit-sharing structure within the partnership model. Farms with better feed efficiency and lower mortality rates tend to exhibit a better R/C ratio, but these profits may decrease due to unstable raw material prices and restrictive contract terms. Several strategies can be implemented, such as Optimizing Feed Efficiency (introducing feeding schedules and controlling feed formulation quality), Reducing Mortality (enhancing vaccination programs and disease monitoring protocols), Price Transparency in Partnerships (renegotiating contract terms to enable a fairer revenue distribution for smallholder farmers), and Data Monitoring Tools (adopting digital monitoring technologies for feed intake, weight gain, and mortality tracking to enable real-time adjustments).

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